

FREQUENCY OF HYPOGLYCEMIA IN PATIENTS WITH LIVER CIRRHOSIS PRESENTING AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Background

Liver cirrhosis is associated with profound metabolic derangements due to impaired hepatic glucose regulation. Hypoglycemia has an underappreciated complication, although it has the potential clinical consequences, while hyperglycemia and diabetes are well known. Data, particularly from developing countries, regarding the burden of hypoglycemia among patients of liver cirrhosis, is limited.

Objective

To determine the frequency of hypoglycemia among patients with liver cirrhosis presenting to a tertiary care hospital.

Methods

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted on adult patients presenting to a tertiary care hospital aged 28 to 70 years old with clinically, biochemically, and radiologically confirmed liver cirrhosis in the Department of General Medicine at Medical Teaching Institution Mardan Medical Complex, over a time period of six months. Blood glucose levels were tested immediately at presentation or measured within 24 hours of admission by using standardized methods. Blood glucose level below 70 mg/dL were defined as Hypoglycemia. Child–Pugh class and MELD score. The Demographic and clinical variables were also recorded during the study. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize results, and chi-square tests were applied to find the relation between hypoglycemia and selected clinical variables. All the data were analyzed using SPSS version 27.

Results

A total of 151 patients with confirmed liver cirrhosis were included, with a mean age of 51.3 ± 9.4 years; 36.8% female and 64.2% were male. In 77 patients with the overall frequency of 51.0% hypoglycemia was observed in 77. The rise in percentage of hypoglycemia is observed with advancing liver disease severity, occurring more commonly in Child–Pugh class C compared with classes A and

B; but this association had no statistical significance ($p = 0.232$). No prominent linkage was found between hypoglycemia and residential background, sex or diabetes mellitus status.

Conclusion

Hypoglycemia affected almost half of the studied population and was recognized as a common metabolic abnormality among confirmed liver cirrhosis patients presented to the Medical Teaching Institution, Mardan Medical Complex. Hypoglycemia occurred across all stages of cirrhosis, with which it was more common in advanced liver disease. These study findings highlight the significance of regular glucose measurement in patients with liver cirrhosis to promote early diagnosis in patients and appropriate clinical management.

INTRODUCTION

Liver cirrhosis represents a major and growing global health burden, accounting for substantial morbidity, mortality, and healthcare utilization worldwide¹. The long-term liver injury results from different root causes, which include chronic viral hepatitis, alcohol-related liver issues, and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, and the latter, now emerging as a main cause in many areas, are the final pathway of liver cirrhosis^{2,3}. Cirrhosis is mostly understood as a systemic disease with severe metabolic and endocrine consequences beyond its well-recognized structural and portal hypertensive complications⁴. Among these, disturbances in glucose homeostasis are specifically more significant because they reflect the main role of the liver in insulin metabolism, glycogen storage, and gluconeogenesis^{5,6}. While the center of focus that has received considerable attention is hyperglycemia and hepatogenous diabetes while hypoglycemia in patients with advanced liver disease remains a relatively under-recognized metabolic complication⁷.

The pathophysiology of hypoglycemia in cirrhosis is multifactorial and closely related to the severity of hepatic dysfunction⁸. Progressive loss of functional hepatocyte mass leads to impaired gluconeogenesis and diminished hepatic glucose output, particularly during fasting or acute stress⁵. In parallel, hepatic glycogen stores are markedly reduced, limiting the liver's ability to buffer fluctuations in plasma glucose levels. Altered insulin clearance due to portosystemic shunting and reduced hepatic extraction results in peripheral hyperinsulinemia, further predisposing patients to hypoglycemia^{7,9}. Additional

contributory factors include protein-calorie malnutrition, which is highly prevalent in cirrhosis, as well as intercurrent infections and sepsis that increase glucose utilization and blunt counter-regulatory hormonal responses¹⁰. Despite these well-described mechanisms, hypoglycemia in cirrhosis is often underestimated in routine clinical practice, partly because it is perceived as less common than hyperglycemia. Yet, it may be sudden, recurrent, and potentially fatal¹¹.

Clinically, hypoglycemia in patients with liver cirrhosis is associated with serious adverse outcomes. Episodes of low plasma glucose may precipitate or exacerbate hepatic encephalopathy, contribute to cardiac arrhythmias, and increase the risk of falls and trauma, particularly in hospitalized or frail patients^{7,8}. Several studies have linked hypoglycemia in cirrhotic patients to higher rates of intensive care unit admission, prolonged hospital stay, and increased short-term mortality^{7,8}. Importantly, the diagnosis of hypoglycemia in this population is challenging. Autonomic and neuroglycopenic symptoms such as confusion, altered consciousness, and behavioral changes may overlap with manifestations of hepatic encephalopathy, leading to misattribution and delayed recognition¹². As a result, hypoglycemia may remain undetected unless actively screened for, especially in non-diabetic patients with advanced liver disease.

Hypoglycemia is common among patients who are already suffering from liver cirrhosis, according to the available international evidence, particularly in those with decompensated disease. The prevalence rates, which are documented, have large differences across studies, representing the

differences in study design, patient characteristics, cirrhosis severity, and methods of glucose level measurement^{8,13}. However, most of the present documented data comes from developed countries, which have relatively well-resourced healthcare systems. Due to the scarcity of strong data from developing countries, including South Asia, the burden of chronic liver disease is very high, and patients often present at more advanced stages of illness^{14,15}. In countries like Pakistan, factors such as delayed presentation to hospital or delayed treatment, less resources to specialized care, high rates of malnutrition, and a high prevalence of infections may increase the risk and clinical impact of hypoglycemia in cirrhosis¹⁶. Local epidemiological data are therefore significant to properly recognize the magnitude of this problem and to inform relevant clinical strategies.

In view of these considerations, there is a clear need to evaluate hypoglycemia as a clinically relevant but under-studied complication of liver cirrhosis in resource-limited settings. Determining its frequency among cirrhotic patients presenting to tertiary care hospitals can provide an evidence base for heightened clinical vigilance and routine glucose monitoring in this vulnerable population. The primary objective of the present study is to determine the frequency of hypoglycemia among patients with liver cirrhosis presenting to a tertiary care hospital. Improved understanding of its burden may facilitate earlier detection, guide monitoring protocols, and ultimately contribute to better metabolic management and outcomes in patients with advanced liver disease.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

To find the frequency of hypoglycemia among patients with liver cirrhosis, this cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Department of General Medicine. Medical Teaching Institution Mardan Medical Complex, which is a tertiary care teaching hospital in Pakistan, All the Eligible patients were enrolled from the medical outpatient department, emergency department, and medical wards during the study period from **July 2023 to December**

2023. Those patients who required emergency life-saving aid were stabilized as per standard clinical protocols before study-related assessment.

Study Population

The study population consisted of adult patients of either sex, male or female, aged between **28 and 70 years** with confirmed liver cirrhosis, enrolled in the hospital during the study period from **July 2023 to December 2023**. The clinical features (such as jaundice, ascites, peripheral edema, or stigmata of chronic liver disease), biochemical abnormalities suggestive of chronic liver dysfunction, and radiological evidence on abdominal ultrasonography demonstrating a shrunken or coarse liver with surface nodularity, altered parenchymal echotexture, and/or the presence of ascites, these all of which are included in the diagnosis of liver cirrhosis. To support the diagnosis, all the available prior medical records and imaging reports were reviewed. All the recruited patients were enrolled consecutively to minimize selection bias.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

All those patients were included who are adult from 28 to 70 years old (1) with confirmed liver cirrhosis diagnosed on bases of clinical, biochemical, and radiological assessment (2) and provision of written informed consent to willingly participate in the study(3)

Patients were excluded from the study for clinically justified reasons that could have complicated glucose metabolism or were diagnosed by other assessment methods rather than clinical, biochemical, and radiological assessments. The exclusion criteria included (1) Those patient who had known diabetes mellitus receiving insulin or insulin secretagogues (such as sulfonylureas), due to their independent risk of hypoglycemia; (2) those who had acute liver failure, as its metabolic profile differs substantially from chronic cirrhosis; (3) those who had end-stage chronic kidney disease; (4) those females who were pregnant; (5) patients with overt sepsis at presentation; and (6) those who declined to provide informed consent to willingly participate in the study.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The World Health Organization (WHO) sample size calculator was used to calculate the sample size. Based on previously published regional data prevalence of hypoglycemia is 67% among patients with liver cirrhosis, so this assumed prevalence was used. The minimum required sample size was calculated to be **151 patients** with a **95% confidence level** and a **7.5% margin of error**. All the eligible patients presenting to the hospital during the study period were recruited through a non-probability consecutive sampling technique until the desired sample size was achieved.

Data Collection Procedure

Information regarding patient age, sex, body mass index, area of residence, and the clinically relevant history was collected using a pre-designed structured proforma and reported after the confirmation of eligibility and recruitment. At the presentation to the concerned department of the tertiary care hospital, patients underwent clinical evaluation by the treating medical team.

At the time of presentation, blood glucose levels of the patients were measured depending on the clinical context, either random capillary blood glucose or fasting. Use of a standardized technique was done to collect capillary blood samples via finger prick, and a calibrated hospital-approved glucometer that was regularly quality-checked according to institutional protocols was used to measure the blood glucose level. The blood glucose concentration below **70 mg/dL** was defined as hypoglycemia in accordance with widely accepted clinical guidelines. And as part of routine care, clinically indicated, confirmatory venous plasma glucose measurements were also obtained.

Study Variables

The presence of hypoglycemia, defined as a blood glucose level below 70 mg/dL at presentation, was the primary outcome variable. Demographic factors such as age and sex, and clinical characteristics are considered as independent variables. From available investigations and from clinical history, the root cause of liver cirrhosis was also recorded. The severity of disease was measured using standard clinical parameters

Child Pugh classification is done on the basis of clinical and laboratory data documented in the medical record, and all the patients were categorized according to this classification. As potential modifiers, the additional comorbid conditions, like smoking status and hypertension, were also recorded.

Data Analysis

IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 27 was used to analyse the data. Continuous variables were measured for normality and expressed as mean with standard deviation or median with interquartile range, as appropriate. Categorical variables were summarized as frequencies and percentages. The hypoglycemia as the primary outcome was documented as a proportion of the total recruited patient. Stratification by demographic and clinical variables, where it was applicable, was also performed to explore patterns within subgroups. A p-value below **0.05** was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

The Institutional Ethical Review Committee of Mardan Medial Complex approved the Protocol of this study. After explaining the purpose and procedures of the study, a written informed consent was obtained from all the recruited patients to willingly participate in the study. According to the institutional and ethical guidelines, participant confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the study. This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki.

Results

Baseline Characteristics of the Study Population

A total of **151 patients** with confirmed liver cirrhosis were included in the analysis. The mean age of the study population was **51.3 ± 9.4 years**. Male patients constituted **64.2% (n = 97)**, while **35.8% (n = 54)** were female. Most patients belonged to a **rural background (67.5%)**, and more than half were from a **lower socioeconomic class (51.7%)**.

With respect to disease severity, 46.4% (n = 70) of patients were classified as Child–Pugh class B, followed by 34.4% (n = 52) in class C and 19.2% (n = 29) in class A. The mean MELD score was 16.8 ± 5.5 . Ascites and hepatic encephalopathy were present in 57.0% and 33.8% of patients,

respectively. The most common etiology of cirrhosis was hepatitis C virus infection (49.0%), followed by hepatitis B (19.9%) and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (18.5%). Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of patients with liver cirrhosis (n = 151)

Variable	Value
Age (years), mean \pm SD	51.3 \pm 9.4
Male sex, n (%)	97 (64.2)
Rural residence, n (%)	102 (67.5)
Lower socioeconomic status, n (%)	78 (51.7)
Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	33 (21.9)
Hypertension, n (%)	43 (28.5)
Ascites, n (%)	86 (57.0)
Hepatic encephalopathy, n (%)	51 (33.8)
Gastrointestinal bleeding, n (%)	28 (18.5)
Child–Pugh class A, n (%)	29 (19.2)
Child–Pugh class B, n (%)	70 (46.4)
Child–Pugh class C, n (%)	52 (34.4)
MELD score, mean \pm SD	16.8 \pm 5.5
Hepatitis C etiology, n (%)	74 (49.0)

Frequency of Hypoglycemia

Hypoglycemia (blood glucose <70 mg/dL) was observed in 77 patients, yielding an overall frequency of 51.0% among patients with liver cirrhosis. Blood glucose measurements were obtained at presentation in 70.9% of patients, while 29.1% were measured within 24 hours of admission. Capillary glucose estimation using a glucometer was the predominant method (83.4%).

Association Between Hypoglycemia and Disease Severity

When stratified by Child–Pugh class, the frequency of hypoglycemia increased with advancing liver disease severity. Hypoglycemia was present in 37.9% of patients with Child–Pugh class A, 51.4% with class B, and 57.7% with class C cirrhosis. However, this association did not reach statistical significance ($\chi^2 = 2.92$, $p = 0.232$). The distribution of hypoglycemia across Child–Pugh classes is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Association between hypoglycemia and Child–Pugh class

Child–Pugh Class	Hypoglycemia Present n (%)	Hypoglycemia Absent n (%)
A (n = 29)	11 (37.9)	18 (62.1)
B (n = 70)	36 (51.4)	34 (48.6)
C (n = 52)	30 (57.7)	22 (42.3)
Chi-square (χ^2)	2.92	
p-value	0.232	

Association Between Hypoglycemia and Other Factors

No statistically significant association was observed between hypoglycemia and sex ($p = 0.875$), diabetes mellitus ($p = 0.946$), or residential status ($p = 0.490$). All chi-square tests met validity assumptions, with no expected cell count less than five.

Summary of Findings

In this cross-sectional study, hypoglycemia was identified in approximately half of the patients with liver cirrhosis. Although a higher frequency of hypoglycemia was observed with increasing disease severity, the association was not statistically significant.

Discussion

This cross-sectional study emphasized hypoglycemia as a recurrent and clinically applicable metabolic abnormality among patients with liver cirrhosis presenting to Medical Teaching Institution, Mardan Medical Complex. These findings highlighted that derangements in glucose homeostasis were common in this population and were detected across different stages of liver disease. Even though hypoglycemia appeared more prevalent with increasing severity of cirrhosis, the association did not reach statistical significance. From a clinical viewpoint, the results bulletproof the importance of recognizing hypoglycemia as a routine yet often overlooked complication of cirrhosis, mainly in settings where patients commonly present with advanced disease and several comorbidities.

The regularity of hypoglycemia observed in this study was approximately similar to reports from international research over the past several years, yet significant variation has been noted across studies. The investigations from East Asia and Europe have reported hypoglycemia prevalence ranging from approximately one-third to more than half of hospitalized cirrhotic patients, depending on disease severity, the patient selection, and the diagnostic criteria used^{7,8}. Studies concentrating on hospitalized cohorts have a tendency to report higher frequencies, while those including stable outpatients often

validate lower rates^{3,8}. The differences in glucose capacity methods, timing of sampling, and whether symptomatic or biochemical hypoglycemia was considered also contribute to heterogeneity across studies. The present findings were therefore consistent with the upper range of reported frequencies, in the setting of a tertiary-care setting and the predominance of patients with moderate to advanced liver disease⁸. The data from the South Asia region, and especially from Pakistan, remain limited. The available regional studies have mainly been single-center and have diverse in methodology, but they suggest that hypoglycemia is not unusual among cirrhotic patients in this part of the world^{16,17}. Factors such as delayed healthcare-seeking behavior, high occurrence of virus-related hepatitis, malnutrition, and limited routine metabolic monitoring may increase susceptibility to hypoglycemia in these populations. In Pakistan, patients with cirrhosis often present at later stages of disease, often with complications such as ascites, encephalopathy, or infections, which may further disturb glucose regulation. The current study thus adds locally relevant evidence by systematically evaluating hypoglycemia in a well-defined unit from a tertiary care hospital in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, addressing an important gap in regional works¹⁷.

Findings can be interpreted in light of established pathophysiological mechanisms linking liver cirrhosis and hypoglycemia. Progressive loss of functional hepatocyte mass leads to reduced gluconeogenesis and reduced hepatic glucose output, mainly during fasting or physiological stress. In addition, cirrhotic patients have markedly diminished hepatic glycogen reserves, limiting their capacity to maintain euglycemia during periods of enlarged demand. Different insulin clearance due to portosystemic shunting results in relative hyperinsulinemia, which may further predispose to hypoglycemia even in non-diabetic individuals¹⁸. Malnutrition and sarcopenia, which are highly prevalent in advanced cirrhosis, reduce peripheral glucose buffering capacity and damage counter-regulatory responses. Even though the present study did not demonstrate a statistically significant correlation

between hypoglycemia and Child-Pugh class, the observed trend toward higher frequencies in more advanced disease supports the biological probability of severity-dependent risk⁸.

From a clinical perspective, these findings have important implications for routine practice. Hypoglycemia in cirrhosis may present with non-specific or subtle symptoms that are connected with hepatic encephalopathy, leading to under-recognition and delayed intervention. Failure to identify hypoglycemia promptly can result in avoidable neurological complications, prolonged hospital stay, and increased morbidity. The high frequency observed in this study suggests that the routine glucose monitoring should be considered an integral part of the valuation of patients with cirrhosis, principally in emergency and inpatient settings. Whereas this study did not evaluate treatment strategies or outcomes, early detection alone may facilitate timely supportive measures and closer monitoring in high-risk patients.

The study had several strengths that merit consideration. It was conducted in a tertiary care hospital, capturing a real-world unit of cirrhotic patients representative of routine clinical practice in a resource-limited setting. Clear operational definitions were used for liver cirrhosis and hypoglycemia, and consistent data collection minimized misclassification. The sample size was adequate for valuing the frequency of hypoglycemia and allowed for stratified analyses across clinically relevant subgroups. These features enhance the internal validity and practical relevance of the findings.

On the other hand, certain limitations should be acknowledged. The single-center design may limit the generalizability of the results to other healthcare settings or other regions. The cross-sectional nature of the study precluded assessment of temporal relationships or causal inference between liver disease severity and hypoglycemia. Moreover, long-term outcomes such as mortality, recurrence of hypoglycemic episodes, and their impact on hospitalization duration were not evaluated during the study. Nutritional status and intercurrent infections, which may influence glucose homeostasis, were not assessed in detail. These limitations primarily affect the external

validity and depth of inference rather than the validity of the observed frequency itself.

Future research may focus on multicenter studies across different regions of Pakistan and South Asia as well to provide a more comprehensive epidemiological picture. Longitudinal designs would be valuable in assessing the prognostic significance of hypoglycemia.

Conclusion

Hypoglycemia was identified as a frequent and clinically relevant metabolic abnormality among patients with liver cirrhosis presenting to a tertiary care hospital, affecting approximately half of the studied population. The occurrence of hypoglycemia across all stages of cirrhosis, with a higher proportion observed in patients with more advanced disease, underscores the pervasive nature of impaired glucose regulation in chronic liver disease. Although the association between hypoglycemia and disease severity did not reach statistical significance, the observed trend is biologically plausible and consistent with established pathophysiological mechanisms of progressive hepatic dysfunction.

These findings highlight that hypoglycemia in cirrhosis is not limited to patients with diabetes or those receiving glucose-lowering therapies, but also occurs commonly in non-diabetic individuals, likely reflecting impaired gluconeogenesis, reduced glycogen reserves, altered insulin clearance, and the contribution of malnutrition. Given the potential for hypoglycemia to mimic or worsen hepatic encephalopathy and to contribute to adverse clinical outcomes, its under-recognition may carry important consequences in routine clinical practice.

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